

CRYPTOSPORIDIOSIS: AN UNDERESTIMATED INFECTIONRafia Tabassum^{*1}, Salma Ashraf², Ayesha Aihetasham³, Asma Abdul Latif⁴^{*1,2,3}Institute of Zoology, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan⁴Department of Zoology, Lahore College for Women University, Lahore, Pakistan^{*1}rafiatabassum234@gmail.comDOI: <https://doi.org/>**Keywords**

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Abstract

Cryptosporidium is an enteric protozoan that can cause gastrointestinal diseases, especially in susceptible people like children, the elderly, and those with impaired immune systems. Similar to choleric infection, the illness presents with diarrhea and stomach pain. In the immunocompromised hosts, the parasite causes prolonged infections that can also be fatal. Cryptosporidiosis is therefore regarded as one of the most dangerous opportunistic illnesses for those suffering from acquired immunodeficiency syndrome. Establishing sensitive and targeted diagnostic tests for epidemiological surveillance and morbidity reduction is the most effective method of controlling the infection in these patients. The general features of *Cryptosporidium* infection were outlined here, with an emphasis on the diagnostic instruments that are currently available for the diagnosis of cryptosporidiosis. The development of new diagnostics for cryptosporidiosis and the molecular techniques currently available for its detection are also covered.

INTRODUCTION

Cryptosporidiosis is a water and foodborne zoonotic disease, that affect animals including mammals, birds, fish and reptiles (Fayer, 2010). It is an intracellular protozoan parasite which inhabit the respiratory and digestive tracts of different hosts (Greene, 2006). Many animal species such as pets, reptiles, rodents are thought to serve as reservoirs for cryptosporidium species and can infect humans (Tzipori and Ward, 2002). About 45 species and more than 120 genotypes of *Cryptosporidium* have been found in recent investigations (Xu *et al.*, 2022). According to molecular studies, the most prevalent species that can infect humans are *C. hominis*, *C. canis*, *C. meleagridis* and *C. felis* (Zakir *et al.*, 2021).

Numerous species were also isolated from various hosts. For instance, *C. parvum*, *C. bovis*, *C. andersoni* and *C. ryanae* cause Cryptosporidiosis in cattle; *C. parvum*, *C. ubiquitum*, *C. xiaoi* (Ryan *et al.*, 2014), *C. agni* (Xiao *et al.*, 2004a), *C. bovis*, *C. scrofarum* and *C.*

suis infected sheep; goats have reported to be infected with *C. andersoni* and *C. hominis* (Kaupke *et al.*, 2017). Other hosts that are susceptible to cryptosporidiosis include cats (*C. felis*), dogs (*C. canis*), birds (*C. galli*, *C. meleagridis* and *C. baileyi*), guine pigs (*C. wrari*), reptiles (*C. crotli*), snakes (*C. serpentis*), and lizard (*C. saurophilum*) (Levine 1984; Bogan, 2019; Koudela and Modry, 1998). Furthermore, certain species have been identified. Including *C. anesrinum* in geese, *C. muris* in rodents, *C. caniculus* in rabbits, *C. cervine* in deer, *C. scrofarum* in pig, *C. rhesi* in monkeys and *C. gamhami* in humans (Xiao *et al.*, 2004a). other species have also been isolated from a variety of animals based on geographical range and importance to public health (Baroudi *et al.*, 2018).

HISTORY

In 1895, the first description of *Cryptosporidium* parasites was published. In 1907, Ernest Edward

Tyzzar eventually identified *C. muris* in peptide gland of mice in laboratory (Xiao *et al.*, 2004a). The life cycle of the parasite was later explained in greater detail, and laboratory mice were used to identify second species (Tyzzar, 1912). Prior to being placed in the class Gregarinomorpha, subclass Cryptogregarina, the apicomplexan parasite was categorized as coccidian (Ryan *et al.*, 2016). The parasite still confused with other apicomplexan genera, especially the coccidian genus *Sarcocysts*, about half a century after the *Cryptosporidium* organism was discovered. The reason of this misconception was because a lot of *Sarcocysts* species have thin walled oocysts that often burst to release sporocysts, and each sporocyst contains four sporozoites that resemble the morphology of *Cryptosporidium* oocysts (Xiao *et al.*,

2004a). when the parasite was identified as a cow pathogen in 1971 after being found in an 8-month old calf with chronic diarrhea, it took 70 years before its clinical importance was recognized (Panciera *et al.*, 1971). In Australia, it was later found in lambs with diarrhea (Barker and Carbonell, 1974). Moreover, it wasn't until 1976 that the first biopsy diagnosis of *Cryptosporidium* from a human case was made that its medical significance was acknowledged (Nime *et al.*, 1976). Furthermore, *C. parvum* was identified as a contributing factor to diarrhea in people with acquired immunocompetent people, the parasite is now also recognized as a cause of diarrhea (Cox, 2015).

Figure 1. *Cryptosporidium*: source of infection and mode of transmission

LIFE CYCLE

Infection begins with the intake of oocysts, which contain four sporozoites that hatch at the gut level and release infectious sporozoites (Khalil *et al.*, 2018). After excystation, these sporozoites are absorbed into modified host membrane isolated from the cytoplasm by a thick layer; hence, parasites within the host are extra cytoplasmic rather than intracellular (Chalmers *et al.*, 2018). Within the parasitophorous vacuole, the parasite reproduces asexually or schizogonously, producing 8 merozoites within a type I meront (Bouزيد *et al.*, 2013). Merozoites can penetrate surrounding epithelial cells and spread the infection to other parts of the Intestine. During this stage, merozoites can go through two distinct replicative cycles: an asexual stage characterized by merozoites multiplication (type I meront) and the formation of thin walled oocyst that auto infect the host, and a sexual stage characterized by the formation of type II meront, which after differentiation in microgametocytes and macro gametocytes, will unite to form the zygote ((Tzipori and Ward, 2004). Through a process known as sporogony, the diploid zygote produces four sporozoites within thick or thin walled oocysts. After being released in feces, the thick walled oocyst, protected by a resistant wall, is shed into the environment (Jenkins *et al.*, 2010) (Figure 1).

EPIDEMIOLOGY

Numerous indicators (i.e clinical symptoms) suggests that the frequency of infection is probably 100 times higher than the number of reported cases, even though the number of cryptosporidiosis is cases reported globally in recent years has increased to 3 cases per 100,000 populations (Shrivastava *et al.*, 2017). Cryptosporidiosis seldom effects immunocompetent individuals in underdeveloped nations, although it accounts for 10-15% of instances of severe diarrheal disease, primarily in under five malnourished children (Shoultz *et al.*, 2017). Since many individuals in developing nations still lack access to even the most basic forms of a sanitation and drinking water, the prevalence of cryptosporidium infection is much lower in industrialized nations than in developing ones (Bouزيد *et al.*, 2018).

Many countries have reported outbreaks of cryptosporidiosis linked to contaminated drinking water and swimming pools (Fayer *et al.*, 2000). A small

number of *Cryptosporidium* species, such as *C. hominis*, *C. parvum*, *C. meleagridis*, *C. felis* and *C. canis*, are frequently found in humans despite the fact that there are over 30 species of parasites (Slapeta, 2013; Ayinmode *et al.*, 2018). Although they have different host ranges, *C. hominis* and *C. parvum* are the two species most commonly found in intestinal infections in humans. The former only infects humans, whereas the latter one has infectious cycle that involves many animals (Dixon *et al.*, 2011; Hunter and Thompson 2005). Despite the possibility of animal transmission, it is extremely rare; reports of cryptosporidium infection from sheep, horses, goats and rodents are few (Thompson *et al.*, 2018; Chalmers and Davies, 2010). It has been documented that the dog adapted species, *C. canis* and the cat adapted species *C. felis*, can infect people who are completely healthy (Shrivastava *et al.*, 2017)

PATHOGENESIS

Among the parasites that kill over a million people annually, cryptosporidiosis killed more than 50000 people (Wang *et al.*, 2018; Shirley *et al.*, 2012). Furthermore, according to Bouزيد *et al.* (2013), Adler *et al.* (2017), and Rehn *et al.* (2015), *Cryptosporidium* is one of the most significant protozoan pathogens that cause waterborne outbreaks globally. In addition to the well-established fecal oral transmission, recent research suggests that coughing or inhaling aerosolized droplets through respiratory secretions can also be spread cryptosporidiosis (Sponseller *et al.*, 2014). There have also been reports of pulmonary infections (Riena *et al.*, 2016). In a comparison of individuals with healthy immune system; immunocompromised hosts are more prone to infection, and in HIV/AIDS patients, the parasite frequently results in a chronic, protracted illness that is challenging to cure and may even be fatal. The parasite can induce inflammatory illness of the biliary tree, leading to obstruction in biliary tract, pancreatitis, sclerosing cholangitis and papillary stenosis. Fever and malabsorption are prevalent in these people. According to Wang *et al.* (2018),

Cryptosporidiosis is therefore regarded as one of the most dangerous opportunistic infection for individuals suffering from acquired immune deficiency syndrome.

A *Cryptosporidium* infection typically causes watery diarrhea in immunocompetent individuals, while some may not experience any symptoms (Khalil *et al.*, 2018; Adler *et al.*, 2017). The infection is likely underestimated and underreported, if diarrhea resolves without any medication or treatment (Bouزيد *et al.*, 2013). Peoples who have direct contact with infected animals, especially calves, or who swallow pool water or drink untreated water are more likely to get Cryptosporidiosis infection (Fayer *et al.*, 1997). Additionally, people with weak immune system, poor health (such as those with HIV/AIDS, cancer, or transplant recipients) are more susceptible to this infection (Samie *et al.*, 2014; Florescu *et al.*, 2016; Wang *et al.*, 2018).

DIAGNOSIS

✚ Microscopic identification and Immunochromatography:

In order to diagnose cryptosporidiosis, oocysts with a diameter of 4 to 6 μm are typically seen in the stool of infected individuals using a microscope (Khurana *et al.*, 2018; Ahmad *et al.*, 2018). To rule out a *Cryptosporidium* infection in patients with severe diarrhea, three fecal samples taken on different days should be microscopically analyzed for the presence of oocysts, which can be challenging to detect (Pacheco *et al.*, 2013).

Additionally, the formalin-ether sedimentation method must be used to concentrate the sample before microscopic inspection in order to detect oocysts in feces. On concentrated fecal smears, the oocysts of *Cryptosporidium* can also be seen by phenol-auramine staining or acid-fast (modified Ziehl-Neelsen method) staining, where they stain red and brilliant yellow, respectively

(Khurana *et al.*, 2018). However, as the oocysts may also appear as "ghost" cells, this staining should receive a lot of attention (Vanathy *et al.*, 2017). The microscopic identification of oocysts in fecal smears is typically used for routine diagnosis of cryptosporidiosis; however, this approach, while inexpensive and simple to perform, has a low

sensitivity ($\leq 30\%$). Furthermore, the proficiency of microscopist is crucial for the precise diagnosis of cryptosporidiosis using this method. These techniques, however are unable to differentiate between different species of cryptosporidium (McHardy *et al.*, 2014).

✚ ELISA

The enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and immunochromatographic test, which have good sensitivity and specificity for detecting *Cryptosporidium* antigens, are also used to diagnose cryptosporidiosis (Agnamey *et al.*, 2012; Christy *et al.*, 2012). Previous research has demonstrated that antigen/antibody-based detection techniques are also ineffective if the patient's parasite burden is below the minimal threshold, even though commercial kits have a range of sensitivities and specificities higher than the microscopic methods (ranging from 58 to 95%) (Hawash *et al.*, 2014).

✚ PCR

Microscopy, ELISA, and immunochromatographic tests (ICT) are less convenient in terms of cost, sensitivity, and specificity than PCR, according to earlier research, and they also take longer (Friesen *et al.*, 2018; Laude *et al.*, 2016; Autier *et al.*, 2018). Even while diagnostic tools have advanced significantly (for example, multiplex PCR assays for intestinal protozoa identification are now available), access to this molecular approach is restricted in certain labs and completely nonexistent in others. Additionally, their usage has been restricted because to the cost and need for technical competence, especially in high-prevalence areas like developing nations.

PREVENTION AND CONTROL

The probability of infection is decrease by practicing good personal hygiene and handwashing before preparing and consuming food, after using the restroom, and after coming into with children, cattle, or some animals, as well as with patients who are experiencing diarrhea (Rossle and Latif, 2013). Preventive sanitary measures are crucial to reduce Cryptosporidiosis in agricultural animals. The goal of these preventive methods is to eliminate the parasites outward manifestations and lessen its transmission among animals, the environment, and the host

Aboelsoued and Abdel Megeed (2022). Control measures against cryptosporidiosis are used in livestock husbandry at pens and building used for parturition. These include avoiding high density in the parturition area and during cryptosporidiosis outbreaks, using clean straw beds extensively, and destroying oocysts with an appropriate disinfectant (de Graaf *et al.*, 1999). The danger of *Cryptosporidium* spp. transmission in herd is decreased by limiting animal stocking on farms and separating young or vulnerable animals from adults. Lastly, neonatal animals are protected from cryptosporidium infection by colostrum supply (Aboelsoued and Abdel Mageed, 2022).

Water treatment must be improved by using certain physical and chemical procedures to get rid of *Cryptosporidium* oocysts. Since *Cryptosporidium* is extremely resistant to chlorine disinfection, even at high concentrations and for extended contact times, these methods includes disinfection process like ozone treatment or ultraviolet light irradiation to lower the oocyst viability and infectivity (Betancourt and Rose 2004). Adittionally, the oocysts are plastic and pliable, pores smaller than one micron are necessary (Mendez Hermida *et al.*, 2007). Therefore, membrane microfiltration or ultrafiltration driven by pressure is sufficient to get rid of them. Efficient water supply management is also necessary to prevent secondary contamination during storage, transportation, and usage (Betancourt and Rose, 2004).

CONCLUSION

There are significant shortcomings in the present control programs, particularly with regard to the diagnostic instruments that are available, despite the considerable impact and worldwide occurrence of cryptosporidiosis, which primarily affects immunocompromised people. Furthermore, in endemic locations, the majority of popular diagnostic tests have a tendency to misdiagnose the condition. The most popular approach for detecting cryptosporidium in stool samples is microscopic techniques, and the precision of these methods' diagnosis primarily depends on the microscopist's experience. Since the strongest defense against the virus is early diagnosis, sensitive, specific, simple,

affordable, and high throughput molecular approaches must be developed.

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